

THE ROLE OF LITERATURE AND THE STAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN

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Annotation: this article reflects on literature and dramaturgical activities, which are the sources of formation of socio-cultural skills of preschool children.

Key words: human, child, literature, stage, culture, spirituality, upbringing, manners, morality, goodness, virtue.

РОЛЬ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ И ЭТАП В РАЗВИТИИ ДЕТЕЙ

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Аннотация: в данной статье размышляется о литературе и инсценировке деятельности, которые являются источниками формирования социокультурных умений дошкольников.

Ключевые слова: человек, ребенок, литература, сцена, культура, духовность, воспитание, нравы, нравственность, добро, добродетель.

ADABIYOT VA SAHNING BOLALAR KAMOLOTIDAGI O'RNI

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Annatatsiya: ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar ijtimoiy-madaniy malakalarini shakllantiruvchi manbalar adabiyot va sahnalashtirish faoliyati haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: inson, bola, adabiyot, sahna, madaniyat, ma'naviyat, tarbiya, odob, axloq, ezgulik, fazilat.

Since time immemorial, our great thinkers have written masterpieces for the perfection, maturity, wisdom, manners, aesthetic taste, spirituality, enlightenment and culture of humanity. Nevertheless, the education of mankind continues to improve to this day. From the ancient times to the present, the plays promoted the cultures of their time. Different socio-cultures appear in the specific development of each era.

Literature created in the past serves as a great school for educating children in all aspects in our modern development. It is an important task to inculcate human qualities in the child through staging activities, and to form social and cultural skills. In a person, such qualities as maturity, perfection, magnificence, glory, nobility, and mental health are found in the heart. The encyclopedist Abu Nasr al-Farabi in his work "The City of Virtuous People" says: "The heart is such a main organ that it cannot be controlled by any other part of the body" [1]. All organs of the human body serve the soul. Therefore, it is necessary to embody the qualities of the soul mentioned above in the human "heart".

Arastu (Aristotel) (384-322 BC) in his work "Akhlaqi Kabir" is about intelligence, wisdom, ingenuity, justice, truthfulness, honesty, friendship, humor, humility, intelligence, knowing one's worth, He considered human qualities such as openness, generosity, nobility, bravery, generosity, restraint, courage as "virtues". In Aristotle's work "Akhlaqi Kabir" - "... When considering each virtue, it was said that it is a virtue to think correctly in every field, to act according to reason, to choose the best way"[2]. Aristotle - "If the feelings are pure, but the mind that judges them is misleading, there is no place for virtue. Because virtue comes from pure feelings and intelligence leading to goodness. Therefore, if a person has a virtue, it is

impossible to use it with evil intentions [2]. Virtue is beauty. Virtue is the aim of goodness. Virtuous people are virtuous people. Virtuous people are educated, moral, ethical-aesthetic, cultured people. The owners of beautiful qualities are moral, polite, well-behaved, civilized, spiritual, educated exemplary people.

Our national cultural heritage 3000 years ago, the sacred book of Zoroastrianism, "Firastuyhi..." (the name of one of the religious prayers of the devotees): - I choose a good thought, a good word and a good deed.

I turn away from all bad words and bad deeds[3]. - there is a never-ending instructive thought. A good thought, a good word, a good deed is a sign of people's social culture.

"The Holy Qur'an" teaches the Muslim world to know the truth, to know oneself, to understand the world, to be spiritual, to be cultured, to be economical, not to waste, to be intelligent, to be clean, to be patient, to be grateful. the guide, the one who leads to the right path, the one who encourages to be knowledgeable, the one who invites to speak the truth, the healer, the one who teaches purity, the one who is merciful, the believer, the one who makes one to do good deeds and the one who calls one to be a perfect person, The word of God is an incomparable book that tells about nature and human laws and blessings, the existence and presence of the mighty and wise Lord, and the inevitability of rewards and punishments in this world as well as in this world.

Indeed, for those who are patient and do good deeds, there is forgiveness and a great reward for them[4]. If we look at the fairy tale "Zumrad and Precious" of our people, Zumrad and his father were good, hardworking, nature and birds loving, kind, patient people who did only good deeds. Ultimately, good is rewarded and bad is punished at the end of the tale. Therefore, those who have good thoughts, good words, and good deeds will receive their reward in this world and the next. The holy book "Holy Qur'an" is a divine law that shapes humanity into a person with good morals, good manners, high taste, honest, inculcating values, attaining all the properties of humanity, and civilized.

Spiritual heritage, literature and sacred books play a great role in raising a preschool child into a mature person with good manners, good manners, high taste, honesty, values, and culture. The presentation of fairy tales, parables, narratives and life situations written in literature on the stage gives advice to the child. Watching dramatized works gives children pleasure, makes them happy, and improves their morale. Preschool children learn moral culture, aesthetic culture, speech culture, religious culture, hygienic culture, dressing culture, and other cultures from real and artificial scenes. The child learns by analyzing and imitating what he sees. The role of dramatized plays in the development and culture of preschool children is incomparable!

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